

3-Hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazene as an Indirect Spectrophotometric Reagent for Oxalate, Phosphate, Citrate, and Tartrate

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Recently the fading action of fluoride ions on the colour reaction of ferric—3-hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazene has been reported for the indirect spectrophotometric determination of fluoride in micro quantities¹. The same principle has been utilised for determining oxalate, phosphate, citrate, and tartrate in acidic medium.

Standard ferric chloride, reagent, buffer solutions, and instruments were the same as described earlier.²

FIG. 1

1. Mehra and Sogani, *this Journal*, 1960, 37, 562.

2. Gupta and Sogani, *ibid.*, 1960, 37, 97.

AnalaR oxalic acid, sodium dihydrogen phosphate, citric acid, and tartaric acid were used for preparing standard solutions.

Calibration Curves.— $M \times 10^{-3}$ ferric chloride solutions (5 ml) were pipetted into a set of 50 volumetric flasks. In each flask required amounts of 10% HCl (v/v) and 10% sodium acetate (w/v) solutions were added so as to bring the pH to ~ 3.0 after necessary dilution. It was followed by 10 ml of 0.4% aqueous reagent solution. Different volumes of standard oxalic acid solution were added. The volume was then made to the mark and absorbance was measured at 650 m μ , taking water in the reference cell. Fig. 1, curve I gives the effect of increasing oxalic acid on the fading of blue iron complex. Similarly calibration curves for phosphate, citric acid, and tartaric acid were drawn and shown as curves II, III, and IV respectively. The masking of the reaction is linear only within a certain concentration range, in each case.

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